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Development of Multiblooming Greengram genotypes with Moderate Mosaic Yellow in resistance

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Abstract

The green gram culture VGG04-001 is developed from a cross derivative of K 1 x Vellore local released as VBN (Gg)3 maturing in 65-70 days and suited for cultivation under both under rainfed and irrigated conditions. It has a yield potential of 826 Kg per hectare. It is multiblooming type with moderately resistance to Yellow Mosaic Virus and Powdery Mildew. It possesses desirable characters like high protein content (24.16%). It is recommended for cultivation in Tamil Nadu except Nilgiris and Kanyakumari districts of Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: VGG04-001; Green gram; Yellow Mosaic Virus; Powdery Mildew; Rainfed; Irrigated

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